

PART 4

Digitilisation will make learning easier to digest

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This is the fourth offering in the series of six articles specifically designed to inform, assist and signpost the built environment to embrace and engage on its digital transformation journey. The first part of the series focused on the digitalisation pathway and digital tools, including BIM, that the industry could avail of. The second part of the series (Articles 4, 5 and 6) will look at navigating the pathway to secure the skills advantages to avail of the commercial opportunities that digitalisation offers.

If industry is to develop and leverage its digital skills for energy efficient construction, and increase its competitiveness, it will be driven via the skills of the workforce. Upskilling must be demand-driven ... demand both from the industry perspective and from the workers in the industry. It is this "meeting of demands" that will lead to success in meeting the needs of industry, society and the environment.

Demand needs to be addressed at three different levels :

- (1) Industry – which is profit driven;
- (2) Learner – skills mobility driven;
- (3) The sector – energy reduction driven.

It is evident from our work that the approaches of many EU initiatives are

not interlinked and can, at times, be on opposite faces. So, our challenge is to align all three and harness these in delivering a successful cohesive demand. Stimulation of demand for sustainable energy skills from a learner's perspective is completely different from that of the industry and overall sector need. However, in ARISE (see page ●●) we are aligning these and aiming to create a multilateral inspiration.

How can we stimulate the skills demand necessary to meet industry needs and deliver the energy savings the sector requires?

We can improve market demand and increase the energy performance of buildings by untapping the huge latent potential of the construction workforce through stimulus and reward. Digitalisation is a game-changing strategy that will empower the construction sector to thrive and deliver the expertise for sustainable energy skills. This will be the tool to stimulate demand. There is a direct correlation between digitalisation and energy efficiency as highlighted at the IEA energy efficiency conference in June 2019.

Why?

Most of the issues related to low demand for skilled workforce are due to:

- (1) Lack of a widely-recognised and accepted international scheme

of certified qualifications for sustainable construction and sustainable energy skills;

- (2) Lack of awareness and uptake by the industry of new methods and digitalisation;
- (3) Lack of mandate or incentive by public authorities for the use of such skills.

The digital push is accelerating and, even if construction industry players are still confused and hesitant about the change and new technologies, the time has come for them to develop their digital skills in order to achieve and make their sustainable energy skills more effective.

Our society is in transition, leaving behind the old energy ineffective, material-wasting and not always healthy built environment, and moving towards an energy efficient, healthy and material sustainable built environment. At the same time, digital technology is transforming our lives at an accelerating pace. Digitalisation can be disorientating – standard contexts and work processes that we are all used to are changing. Technologists call this "context collapse".

On the other hand, digitalisation is recognised by those implementing it as a powerful enabler to enhance the effect of their work and as an enrichment of their professional skills. Social interactions and workplaces are changing, and will change further. This is also the fact for upskilling interventions. Due to digitalisation, learning will become easier to access, digest and utilise.

We need to be conscious that sustainable and lean construction is already a reality, but we do not have sufficient skilled professionals and workers to make it become a "normal practice." Furthermore, client and users' awareness and implementation drivers are still lacking (factors which are crucial to increase market demand).

Governments, particularly in the EU, are increasing their CO2 and energy

Paul McCormack with O'Hare McGovern staff who completed the BIMcert training programme.

efficiency regulations and raising their targets, following the EU strategies and policies for decarbonisation of the construction sector and approaching NZEBs. Digitalisation, going hand-in-hand with energy skills, provides a great opportunity to reduce the environmental impact of construction projects. Digitalisation makes the energy skills of the construction workforce more effective and easier to improve. It also provides confirmable effects in rational and smart use of materials and energy.

Digital technologies allow the collaboration of all stakeholders in a collaborative digital environment that is the information carrier of a building's material, environmental and energy properties. Currently we are at the "liminal" stage between the old and the new (liminality comes from the Latin limen, meaning doorway or threshold).

We need to upskill ourselves and society in order to step through the doorway and successfully harvest the benefits in order to address the skills decline. Construction sector employees are also at the liminal threshold of energy transition and digitalisation. In order to successfully stimulate the demand for sustainable energy skills we need to nudge and assist employees to adapt digitalisation and apply it in the context of energy skills.

New patterns

Skills delivery and results must be focused on the development of new patterns to replace the old ways of learning and to form new patterns that demand, stimulate, encourage, unite and assist. We need to provide reassurance that the sustainable digital construction skills transition is supported, clear and identifiable. In order to raise awareness and recommend actions, activities and outputs in training and skills delivery must change to assist and educate the user and industry, therefore

"Push & Pull" demand driver approach.

A: Upskilling scheme; Training access; Accreditation; Validation; Support; Awareness.

B: New norm; Market benchmark; Increase driver demand.

C: Public administration/professional bodies mandate.

D: Further need; Demand stimulus.

further increasing skills demand across the spectrum.

This "skills transformation" process can be achieved using digitalisation and the certification of "step-by-step" competences recognition as an accelerator to empower demand for energy skills.

How?

Unifying digital and energy construction skills and qualifications into an EU-wide recognisable and acceptable construction certification scheme will stimulate demand and also support organisations with delivering quality.

Digital construction (digitalisation), big data and BIM in particular, support sustainability trends in the construction sector, especially the increasing requirements for energy efficiency competences and applicable skills.

Solving the problem of upskilling AEC professionals in digital construction (inc. BIM) requires an holistic approach to sustainable energy. Also, stimulating the demand for sustainable construction and energy skills workforce are closely connected. Recognising that symbiotic, self-generating loop between need and delivery must stimulate the demand by offering a more efficient pathway to upgrading the BIM skills of construction professionals.

Unified programme

A unified programme for sustainable construction qualifications needs to be developed in order to enhance wider market recognition; more intensive demand and more stimulating support must be provided by/and for policy and regulatory frameworks. The result will be a skilled and qualified AEC sector workforce executing works that will help achieve the sustainable energy performance of buildings. Digitalisation is both a skill and a tool. However, people are the true enablers. It is they who will make change towards energy efficiency possible. ■